

Designing Tunnel Support Systems based on Ground Reaction Curve and Equilibrium Strain Approach

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ABSTRACT

When tunneling through a weak rock mass, collapse of the opening is likely to occur if (1) the maximum allowable limit of strain before setting up the support is exceeded or (2) the support pressure given by the installed support system is not adequate to sustain the weight of broken rock resulting from the excavation. This paper presents the results of using the GRC and equilibrium strain approach in designing a tunnel support system. The equilibrium strain is used as a design tool because it has been observed that the final radial deformation of a supported tunnel occurs at the equilibrium between the support and the deforming ground, not at the time of support installation. The allowable strain at the time of support installation is called the critical strain. The approach in this paper uses a large non-circular road tunnel with a mouth profile, excavated through varying rock mass qualities (quantified by Q and RMR). The tunnel models are built in the commercially available computer code Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC). Results from the FLAC model show that after the recommended support system is installed, the amount of vertical deformation and the extent of the plastic zone around the tunnel decrease significantly. This result is achieved because the time to install the support to reach the pre-set equilibrium strain $\epsilon_{eq} = 1\%$ is estimated properly. As a result, the induced bending moment, axial and shear loads in the tunnel lining are well inside the strength envelope of the support system with factor of safety (FoS) = 1.2–2.4 under the combined thrust-bending moment and FoS = 1.6–3.2 under the combined thrust-shear force. This result indicates that the GRC and equilibrium strain approach can be used to design a reliable tunnel support system.

Key Words: Tunnel support, Ground reaction curve, Critical strain, Support reaction curve, Support pressure, Q-system.

INTRODUCTION

The current practice in designing tunnel support systems depends upon the rock mass classification used and the experience of the tunnel designers. When tunneling through a weak mountainous rock mass, designing a tunnel support system is not a trivial task. Tunnel engineers must cope with the estimation of support pressure that is needed to stabilize the tunnel face and the newly-opened room behind the face. In ideal conditions, collapse of the opening is likely to occur if (1) the maximum allowable limit of strain before setting up the support is exceeded or (2) the support pressure given by the installed support system is not adequate to sustain the weight of broken rock resulting from the excavation.

The so-called convergence-confinement method (CCM) has been a standard practice for evaluating the displacement behavior of a tunnel and to determine the required support pressure to control the convergence of the tunnel wall. The CCM consists of the ground reaction curve (GRC), the support reaction curve (SRC), and the longitudinal displacement curve (LDP). The GRC represents the

relationship between the increasing radial displacement of the tunnel wall u_r and the decreasing internal support pressure p_i . The SRC represents the relationship between the increasing support pressure p_s and the increasing radial displacement of the support u_s . Lastly, the LDP represents the radial displacement occurring along the longitudinal axis of the unsupported tunnel.

Figure 1 illustrates the application of the CCM in designing a tunnel support for a circular tunnel with a 5 m radius. Based on the LDP curve, when the support is installed at 5 m behind the face, the tunnel wall already converges to $u_r = 1.5$ cm. Based on the SRC curve, it is observed that the support system does not stop the convergence immediately. Rather, it deforms with the surrounding ground until equilibrium is reached at wall deformation $u_r = 1.6$ cm. Based on the GRC curve, this equilibrium point corresponds to the support pressure $p_s = 0.35$ MPa. Therefore, by using the CCM, tunnel designers can (1) decide when to install the support from the LDP curve, (2) estimate the required support pressure at the time of installation from the GRC curve, and (3) assess the capability of the installed support system to stabilize the tunnel from the SRC curve. From the CCM in Figure 1, the maximum support pressure given by the combined support system (i.e., 3 m long rockbolt and 20 cm thick shotcrete) is 1.2 MPa, while the required support pressure at equilibrium is only 0.35 MPa. Hence, the support is considered capable of sustaining the load given by the deforming rock mass surrounding the tunnel.

Figure 1. Illustration of the CCM for estimating tunnel deformation and support pressure.

In tunneling, the maximum allowable limit of strain (or deformation) before setting up the support is called the critical strain. Beyond the critical strain, the tunnel will become unstable and it will be difficult to provide adequate support (Chern et al., 1998; Hoek, 2001; Sakurai, 1983). As shown in the CCM in Figure 1, the final radial deformation of the supported tunnel is at the equilibrium point, not at the time of support installation (at its critical strain). Thus, it may be desirable to design the support system based on the maximum allowable deformation at the equilibrium because this point will determine the final “deformed” profile of the supported tunnel. Each member of the support

system must be selected so that when this combined support system is installed, the continuing ground deformation will not exceed the pre-set “equilibrium strain”.

While the concept of the equilibrium strain approach may sound interesting, it is not possible to use it in designing a tunnel support system if the GRC, SRC, and LDP curves for the tunnel in question are not available. Although the closed-form solutions to develop the GRC, SRC, and LDP curves are readily available, they are only applicable for circular tunnels (Carranza-Torres & Fairhurst, 2000; Duncan Fama, 1993; Vlachopoulos & Diederichs, 2009). This limitation is unfortunate because tunnel cross-sections in civil and underground mining purposes are commonly non-circular in practice, e.g., horseshoe-shape, rectangular, or even nearly elliptical. On the other hand, two-dimensional (2-D) axisymmetric models cannot be used to develop numerical LDP curves for non-circular tunnels because the non-circular cross-section will invalidate the axisymmetric assumption.

With this gap in mind, the objective of this paper is to carry out a series of numerical simulations for designing a tunnel support system for non-circular tunnels based on the GRC and the equilibrium strain approach. Later, from the GRC and the pre-set equilibrium strain, the time to install the support and the magnitude of the support pressure required to reach equilibrium can be observed. The types and the properties of the support elements can then be selected. Lastly, to examine the performance of the selected support system in stabilizing the deforming ground, the extent of ground deformation and the plastic zone in the ground surrounding the supported tunnel will be analyzed. In particular, the capability of the support system to sustain the induced bending moment, axial and shear loads will be examined through a use support capacity diagram.

2. THE TUNNEL UNDER STUDY

The approach in this paper is demonstrated using a large non-circular road tunnel with a mouth profile, 16 m in width and 10 m in height, excavated through a weak and isotropic rock mass at a depth of 200 m, with in situ stress $\sigma_0 = 5.4$ MPa. Even though the approach is demonstrated using a hypothetical tunnel, the dimensions and depth of the tunnel are commonly observed in major highway tunnels crossing mountainous weak rock masses. Thus, the approach in this paper is expected to be applicable to an actual construction. The tunnel models are built in the commercially available computer code Fast Lagrangian Analysis of Continua (FLAC), which is a 2-D finite difference based computer program for geomechanical applications developed by Itasca (2011a). A close-up view of the FLAC model of the tunnel is shown in Figure 2. The model boundary is stretched up to 100 m in the horizontal direction and 60 m in the vertical direction. It should be noted that the continuum model in FLAC is presented only to provide a preliminary analysis of the proposed concept. For a more comprehensive analysis of ground behavior of tunneling in weak jointed rock masses, the discontinuum modeling approach such as that in the Universal Distinct Element Code or UDEC (Itasca, 2014) would be more realistic than the continuum model in FLAC.

Figure 2. Close-up view of the FLAC model of the tunnel under study (not to scale).

The conditions of the weak rock mass surrounding the tunnel are given in Table 1. As the rock mass conditions along a tunnel alignment are commonly heterogeneous, the rock mass surrounding the tunnel under study is also varied into five different rock mass qualities (Cases 1–5). The varying rock masses are quantified using the rock quality tunneling index or Q-system (Barton, 2002; Barton, Lien, & Lunde, 1974). In Cases 1–5, these weak rock masses are progressively increasing in quality as shown by the increasing value of their rock quality designation or RQD (Deere, 1968) while keeping the other Q parameters constant. The Q-system is one of the two most commonly used rock mass classification systems for tunneling. The other is the Rock Mass Rating (RMR) developed by Bieniawski (1989), and correlations between the two systems are available (Barton, 1995). The Q-system is chosen to represent the weak rock mass in this paper because after 40 years of development with more than 2,000 cases of tunnels/caverns, it is still the most consistent and reliable rock mass classification that gives the best fit between rock quality, excavation dimensions, and support quantities (Barton & Grimstad, 2014). As shown in Table 1, the weak rock mass surrounding the tunnel has $Q = 0.008$ – 0.04 and $RMR = 19$ – 29 , which is classified as exceptionally poor to extremely poor rock masses and very poor to poor rock masses, respectively.

Parameter	Symbol	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5
Rock Quality Designation	<i>RQD</i>	10	15	20	25	30
Joint set number	J_n	20	18	15	14	12
Joint roughness number	J_r	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	1.0
Joint alteration number	J_a	6	6	6	6	6
Joint water reduction factor	J_w	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5
Stress Reduction Factor	<i>SRF</i>	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0	5.0
Rock tunneling quality index (Barton, 2002)	<i>Q</i>	0.008	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04
Classification		Excep. poor	Extrem. poor	Extrem. poor	Extrem. poor	Extrem. poor
Rock Mass Rating (Bieniawski, 1989)	<i>RMR</i>	19	22	25	27	29
Classification		Very poor	Poor	Poor	Poor	Poor
The rock masses are also assumed to have density $\rho = 2,700 \text{ kg/m}^3$, intact Young's modulus $E = 20,000 \text{ MPa}$, Poisson's ratio $\nu = 0.2$, intact uniaxial compressive strength $\sigma_c = 10 \text{ MPa}$, and intact uniaxial tensile strength $\sigma_t = 1 \text{ MPa}$.						

Table 1. Rock mass conditions surrounding the tunnel

$$Q = \frac{RQD}{J_n} \times \frac{J_r}{J_a} \times \frac{J_w}{SRF} \text{ and } RMR = 15 \log Q + 50 \quad (1)$$

The Q-value and RMR in Table 1 are calculated using the following equation: where RQD is the % of competent drill-core sticks ≥ 100 mm in length (Deere, 1968) and J_n , J_r , J_a , J_w and SRF are the Q-system parameters as defined in Table 1.

3. ROCK MASS PARAMETERS FROM THE EMPIRICAL EQUATIONS

The important rock mass parameters to be used in this study are the deformation modulus E_{mass} , Poisson's ratio ν_{mass} , compressive strength σ_{tmass} , uniaxial tensile strength σ_{tmass} , cohesion c_{mass} , and friction angle of the rock mass ϕ_{mass} . The empirical equations to calculate these rock mass parameters are summarized in Table 2 along with the results of the calculation for each rock mass case. The rock mass parameters in this paper are mainly calculated from Q and RMR. However, they can also be calculated from other rock mass classifications that appear in Vászárhelyi and Kovács (2017). The average values from each calculated parameter will then be used as input parameters for the numerical simulations in FLAC to evaluate the deformation behavior of the tunnel and the performance of the selected support system.

Parameter	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4	Case 5	Equation	Reference
Q	0.008	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	$Q = RQD/J_n \times J_r/J_a \times J_w/SRF$	Barton (2002; 1974)
RMR	19	22	25	27	29	$RMR = 15 \log Q + 50$	Bieniawski (1989)
E_{mass} (GPa)	1.67	2.01	2.40	2.68	2.96	$E_{mass} = 10^{\left(\frac{RMR-40}{4}\right)}$	Serafim and Pereira (1983)
	1.70	2.32	2.97	3.41	3.83	$E_{mass} = E \left[0.5 \left(1 - \left\{ \cos \pi \frac{RMR}{100} \right\} \right) \right]$	Mitri et al. (1994)
	0.67	1.09	1.60	1.991	2.40	$E_{mass} = 0.1 \left(\frac{RMR}{10} \right)^3$	Read et al. (1999)
	0.94	1.11	1.31	1.44	1.57	$E_{mass} = 10 \left(Q \frac{\sigma_c}{100} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$	Barton (1996)
	1.66	2.01	2.40	2.68	2.96	$E_{mass} = 10^{(15 \log Q + 40)/40}$	Barton (2002)
Ave.	1.32	1.71	2.14	2.44	2.75		
ν_{mass}	0.41	0.40	0.39	0.38	0.37	$\nu_{mass} = 0.25 \left[1 + \exp^{-\frac{\sigma_{tmass}}{4}} \right]$	Aydan et al. (1993)
	0.39	0.38	0.37	0.37	0.37	$\nu_{mass} = 0.5 - 0.2 \frac{RMR}{RMR + 0.2(100 - RMR)}$	Tokashiki and Aydan (2010)
	0.44	0.43	0.42	0.42	0.41	$\nu_{mass} = \nu \left[2.5 - 1.5 \frac{RMR}{RMR + (100 - RMR)} \right]$	Aydan et al. (2012)
Ave.	0.42	0.41	0.40	0.39	0.38		
c_{mass} (MPa)	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04	0.05	$c_{mass} = \frac{RQD}{J_n} \times \frac{1}{SRF} \times \frac{\sigma_c}{100}$	Barton (2002)
	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	$c_{mass} = \frac{\sigma_{tmass}}{2} \times \frac{(1 - \sin \phi_{mass})}{\cos \phi_{mass}}$	Mohr-Coulomb criterion
Ave.	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5		
ϕ_{mass} (°)	29	31	33	34	34	$\phi_{mass} = 20 + 0.5RMR$	Aydan and Kawamoto (2001)
	5	5	5	5	5	$\phi_{mass} = \tan^{-1} (J_r/J_a \times J_w)$	Barton (2002)
	23	24	25	26	26	$\phi_{mass} = 20 \sigma_{tmass}^{0.25}$	Aydan et al. (2012)
Ave.	19	20	21	21	22		
σ_{tmass} (MPa)	0.04	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	$\sigma_{tmass} = \sigma_t \frac{RMR}{RMR + 6(100 - RMR)}$	Aydan et al. (1993)
	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.03	$\sigma_{tmass} = 0.029 \gamma Q^{0.31}$	Singh and Goel (2011)
	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	$\sigma_{tmass} = 5 \gamma \left(Q \frac{\sigma_c}{100} \right)^{\frac{1}{3}}$	Barton (2000)
Ave.	0.21	0.26	0.30	0.33	0.36		
						(Barton, 1993)	Kalamaras and Bieniawski

σ_{cmass}	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	$\sigma_{cmass} = \sigma_c \times \exp\left(\frac{RMR-100}{24}\right)$	Kalamaras and Bieniawski (1993)
(MPa)	0.6	0.7	0.8	0.9	1.0	$\sigma_{cmass} = \sigma_c 10^{(0.012RQD-1.34)}$	Bhasin and Grimstad (1996)
	3.8	4.5	5.3	5.9	6.4	$\sigma_{cmass} = 7\gamma Q^{1/3}$	Singh and Goel (2011)
	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	$\sigma_{cmass} = \sigma_c \times \exp\left(\frac{RMR-100}{20}\right)$	Sheorey (1997)
	1.5	1.9	2.3	2.5	2.8	$\sigma_{cmass} = 0.5 \exp^{0.06RMR}$	Trueman (1998)
	1.3	1.5	1.8	1.9	2.1	$\sigma_{cmass} = 5\gamma \left(Q \frac{\sigma_c}{100}\right)^{1/3}$	Barton (2000)
	1.5	1.9	2.3	2.5	2.8	$\sigma_{cmass} = 0.5 \exp(0.06RMR)$	Asef et al. (2000)
Ave.	1.7	2.0	2.4	2.7	2.9		
σ_{cmass}/σ_o	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5		

Table 2. The calculated rock mass parameters based on the empirical equations

4. SIMULATION RESULTS

4.1. Developing the GRC curve

The ground reaction curve is developed by applying an incrementally decreasing amount of internal support pressure p_i while storing the corresponding tunnel closure u_y . For the tunnel under study, the internal support pressures along the tunnel boundary are reduced in %30 increments from $p_i = 5.4$ MPa (corresponding to the in situ condition before the excavation, $u_y = 0$ cm) to zero (corresponding to the fully excavated ground, u_y is at its maximum amount). Figure 3 presents the GRC curves of the tunnel under study for all varying rock mass qualities resulting from the FLAC simulations. In Figure 3, the corresponding axis for the vertical strain U_y is also shown with the u_y axis (see the inset equations to calculate u_y and E_y). Note that for rock masses with $Q = 0.08$ and 0.01 , at $p_i < 1$ MPa, the tunnel continues to deform and will collapse if it is not supported. For the other rock masses with slightly improved quality, $Q = 0.03, 0.02$, and 0.04 , the tunnel will reach its maximum tunnel closure at $u_y = 23, 45$, and 18 cm, respectively, corresponding to $E_y = 2.3, 4.5$, and %1.8, respectively.

Figure 3. The GRC curves of the tunnel for varying rock mass qualities.

4.2. Developing the equilibrium strain curve

As mentioned earlier, the critical strain E_{crit} is defined as the maximum allowable strain that the tunnel may undergo before setting up the support. The value of the critical strain will vary from tunnel to tunnel and depend on the observed ground deformation. Sakurai (1983) and Chern et al. (1998) proposed that $E_{crit} > \%1$ will be the onset of tunnel instability, while Hoek (2001) and Singh et al. (1997) suggested that a tunnel may undergo strains $E_{crit} = \%6-5$ without having stability problems. However, the GRC curves for $Q = 0.008$ and 0.01 in Figure 3 indicate that it is not possible to allow the tunnel under study to undergo $E_y = \%5$ to reach minimum levels of support pressure as the collapses have occurred at $E_y = 12$ and $\%20$, respectively. This circumstance reinforces the need to use the equilibrium strain approach instead of the critical strain approach for designing a tunnel support system.

In this paper, the equilibrium strain E_{eq} is defined as the maximum allowable vertical strain after the support is installed. In other words, the equilibrium strain defines the maximum allowable tunnel closure at the equilibrium between the support and the deforming ground. The equilibrium strain for each rock mass quality is developed from Figure 3. The results are shown in Figure 4 and can be considered as the pre-set equilibrium strain curves. For example, the equilibrium strain for the tunnel under study is set to be $E_{eq} = \%1$. From the curve for $E_{eq} = \%1$ in Figure 4, it can be observed that the required support pressure to stop the deforming ground at the equilibrium would be 0.6, 0.9, 1.2, 1.8, and 0.4 MPa for rock masses with $Q = ,0.008$ 0.03 ,0.02 ,0.01, and 0.04, respectively.

Figure 4. The pre-set equilibrium strain curves of the tunnel for varying rock mass qualities.

4.3. Selecting the tunnel support system

Based on the Q-system, for the tunnel under study, with its largest span of 16 m (Span = 16 m) and its function as a major road tunnel (ESR = 1), the recommended support systems for varying rock mass qualities along the tunnel alignment would be those in regions 8 and 7 in the Q-support chart (see Figure 5a). For simplicity in the FLAC model, all cases are supported by the combination of fiberreinforced shotcrete S(fr) + bolt (B) + rib reinforced shotcrete arches (RRS) with S(fr) = 25 cm thick, B = 4 m long, RRS = 55 cm thick (see Figure 5b). The material properties of each member of the supporting elements are taken from the literature (Carranza-Torres & Fairhurst, 2000; Chryssanthakis et al., 1997; Itasca, 2011b; Prassetyo, 2017; Prassetyo & Gutierrez, 2016) and used as the input parameters for the structural elements in the FLAC models.

4.4. Assessing the performance of the selected support system

Due to limited space, only the performance of the support systems for two rock mass qualities ($Q = 0.008$ and 0.02) will be assessed. Figure 6 shows that for each rock mass quality, the amount of vertical deformation in the roof and floor are greatly reduced from 30–20 cm in the unsupported tunnels to only 5 cm in the supported tunnels. This value corresponds to 10 cm in total closure or $E_{eq} = \%1$ as expected. The extent of the plastic zone in Figure 7 shows a similar result. It can be seen that the plastic zones in the surrounding ground of the supported tunnels no longer exist. In the unsupported tunnels, the extent of these plastic zones goes up to 20 m from the tunnel boundary.

Figure 5. Plots of (a) the Q-support chart indicating the regions of the recommended tu system and (b) the arrangement of recommended support system in all FLAC m

Figure 6. Comparison of the extent of vertical deformation.

Figure 7. Comparison of the extent of plastic zone.

Figure 8 illustrates the resulting GRC and SRC curves at equilibrium strain for rock masses with $Q = 0.008$ and 0.02 . From Figure 8, it can be observed that for a specific rock mass quality, the time to install the support to reach the pre-set equilibrium strain $E_{eq} = \%1$ can be estimated and should be when the tunnel closure reaches $u_y = 5$ and 8 cm for $Q = 0.008$ and 0.02 , respectively.

Because the factor of safety (FoS) of the selected support system is hard to know, the support capacity diagrams are constructed to obtain a rough estimate of the FoS of this combined support system. Figure 9 presents the thrust-moment and thrust-shear force capacity diagrams for rock masses with $Q = 0.008$ and 0.02 . The strength properties of the tunnel support are factorized in such a way that the induced bending moments, axial and shear loads in the lining are located inside the strength envelope of the estimated FoS. It can be seen that the estimated FoS of the support system is increased with the increase of rock mass quality as expected and that the support system is more prone to fail under bending (FoS = 1.7–1.2) than under shearing (FoS = 2.3–1.6). In general, the results show that the selected support systems are capable of sustaining the load from the deforming ground, even in the worst rock mass quality ($Q = 0.008$). The equilibrium strain at $E_{eq} = \%1$ is never exceeded because the time to install the support can be predicted.

Figure 8. Plots of GRC and SRC curves showing deformation stopped at $\epsilon_{eq} = 1\%$.

Figure 9. The support capacity diagrams.

5. CONCLUSION

The objective of this paper was to carry out a series of numerical simulations for designing tunnel support systems for non-circular tunnels based on the GRC and the equilibrium strain approach. The results show that designing a support system for tunneling through weak rock masses is not a trivial task. However, by optimizing the use of the GRC and the equilibrium strain approach, a safe support design can be achieved. Results from the FLAC model show that after the recommended support system was installed, the amount of vertical deformation and the extent of the plastic zone around the tunnel decrease significantly. This result is achieved because the time to install the support to reach the pre-set equilibrium strain $\epsilon_{eq} = 1\%$ was estimated properly. As a result, the induced bending moment, axial and shear loads in the tunnel lining are well inside the strength envelope of the support system with $FoS = 2.4-1.2$ under the combined thrust-bending moment and $FoS = 3.2-1.6$ under the combined thrust-shear force. In summary, the GRC and equilibrium strain approach proved to be helpful in designing a tunnel support system.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support from the University Transportation Center for Underground Transportation Infrastructure (UTC-UTI) at the Colorado School of Mines for funding this research under Grant No. 69A3551747118 from the U.S. Department of Transportation (DOT). The opinions expressed in this paper are those of the authors and not the US DOT.

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